

Mendel
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The international research and practical conference

THE DEVELOPMENT
OF NATURE SCIENCES:
PROBLEMS
AND SOLUTIONS

BRNO, the Czech Republic,
April 27-28, 2018

Mendel
University
in Brno

**European Network
for Academic Integrity**

**Black Sea Research Institute
of Economy and Innovation**

The international research and practical conference
**THE DEVELOPMENT OF NATURE SCIENCES:
PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS**

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*Flora i Vegetation,
Zoology,
Medico-biological research*

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Адаптивна селекція пшениці м'якої озимой на стійкість к грибовим захворюванням с использованием еколого-географически отдаленных форм Рябовол Я. С., Диордиева И. П., Коцюба С. П., Новак Ж. М., Новак А. В.	56
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**CONDITION PHOTOSYNTHETIC APPARATUS
OF *ACER PLATANOIDES* L. AND *ACER TATARICUM* L.
ON THE TERRITORY OF SANITARY-PROTECTIVE ZONE
“S. KOVALSKA RCS” IN THE CITY OF KYIV**

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In the large industrial cities of Ukraine, in particular, in the city of Kyiv, woody plants play an important role in optimizing the environment for human existence and development and biogeocenosis in general. The impact of industrial enterprises may be reflected in lowering the concentration of chlorophyll in plant leaves, the productivity of photosynthesis, weakening and loss of trees.

Photosystem II (FSII) plays a central role in the generation and regulation of electronic transport, which is carried out in chloroplasts of plant leaves. Performance indicators of FSII are an important component of the activity monitoring the photosynthetic apparatus (FSA) [1]. In our study, it was assumed that the value of the activity index FSA leaves of trees can be used for reveal influence working of construction enterprises on the development and condition of trees on territory of the sanitary protection zone.

The measuring of indicators was carried out on the sanitary-protection zone territory of public joint-stock company “S. Kovalska Reinforced Concrete Structures Plant”, which works in the city of Kiev and it most powerful producer of concrete and reinforced concrete structures in Ukraine. During the research, the experimental measurements points were selected in within the 300-meter sanitary protection zone of the construction plant, and the control

measurements points on the territory remote from the impact of construction enterprise, that is, on the Navodnitsky Park territory.

At the Plant S. Kovalska Reinforced Concrete Structures annual production of concrete mixtures is 1200000 m³, reinforced concrete products 200000 m³. Ten workshops and 8 subdivision of concretes mixing provide the production of 4000 m³ of concrete mixes everyday [2]. With such a volume of reinforced concrete products production per year, on the plant's sanitary protection zone territory ins atmosphere coming significant amount of aerosols. They fall in to atmosphere from the welding shops of the reinforcement, from the places of unloading cement, sand, gravel, as well as cement loading places with pneumatic conveyor to bunkers and concrete mixers. The created aerosols are saturated with CO₂, MnO₂, MgO₂ and dust cement particles, the size of which does not exceed 5 μm [3], therefore their excessive concentration in atmospheric air can be considered as a factor of decrease photosynthesis efficiency in leaves of trees.

On the sanitary-protection zone territory of public joint-stock company "S. Kovalska Reinforced Concrete Structures Plant" among the species of trees, was *A. platanoides* and *A. tataricum* identified. The species *A. platanoides* is characterized by of a sensitivity to the fertilities, moisture and salinity of the soil, grows fast, tolerant to shadow, heats-resistant, withstands frost to minus 40 °C, early spring frost him it is not damaged, but sensible to excessive fume in air. In unlike him, *A. tataricum* is unpretentious to the fertility and moisture of the soil, it is able adapt to dust and gas pollution [4].

In the experiment was used leaves, cut off summer from the upper and lower layers crones of tree, in the sanitary protection zone of factory (experimental leaves) and beyond, in Novodnitsky Park (control leaves). The functional condition photosynthetic apparatus of leaves of *A. platanoides*, and *A. tataricum* was estimated in comparisons with the control leaves, from the indices of chlorophyll fluorescence induction using an XE-PAM fluorometer ("Walz", Germany). The effect of the concentration of Mn and dust particles was evaluated by the ratio of F_v/F_0 based on the method described in article [5]. The effect of Mg was evaluated by $PI_{(ABS)}$ [6], based on the method described in [7] using the Handy PEA fluorometer [8]. The using of index of fluorescence chlorophyll F_v/F_0 for identify Mn is consistent with the results obtained earlier by the researchers on other plant species [9]. This index is very sensitive to insignificant changes in the concentration of Mn [10, 11].

As a result of the experiment, a direct correlation was found between the concentration of Mn, Mg and the fluorescence intensity of chlorophyll *A. platanoides* and *A. tataricum* leaves ($r = 0.83$). On the territory of the sanitary protection zone of the plant of building structures, where average photon flux density of 720 μmol / m² s⁻¹ in the leaves *A. platanoides*, adapted to darkness, the chlorophyll fluorescence parameter (F_v/F_0) in averaged

2.08±0.16, what is 1.3 times less, than in control leaves that developed on a site remote from the plant within Navodnitsky Park (Fig.). In the leaves *A. tataricum* that developed on the territory of the sanitary protection zone of the manufacture of building structures, the parameter (F_v/F_0) was on average 1.5 times more, than in leaves of *A. platanoides*, which is probably due from of better adaptation of the leaves of *A. tataricum* to the influence Mn.

In the sanitary protection zone of the building construction plant in similar lighting conditions, the PI_{ABS} performance of index in the *A. platanoides* was 2.7 times less compared to the control leaves and 4.4 times less, than in the *A. tataricum* leaves that developed on the same territory under similar conditions. The low performances of index PI_{ABS} (0.49±0.17) of the chlorophyll fluorescence in the *A. platanoides* leaves, that developed within the sanitary protection zone of building manufacture, indicates an excessive receipt of Mg from the manufacture to the environment. Under these conditions, *A. platanoides* showed a low ability to adapt to gas and dust pollution of atmospheric air.

Fig. Parameters of the chlorophyll fluorescence (F_v / F_0) and performance of index (PI_{ABS}) FSI of leaves of *A. platanoides* and *A. tataricum* with different concentrations of Mn (A) and Mg (B) at a photon flux density (PFD) of $720 \mu\text{mol} / \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{c}^{-1}$ in the territories: Control – of Navodnitsky Park; SPZ – of sanitary protection zone of the construction plant in the Kiev city

On the Based values of performances fluorescence chlorophyll F_v/F_0 , it was found that, the concentration of Mn in the leaves of *A. platanoides*, was less by 34.4% compared to the leaves of *A. tataricum*. The value performance of index PI_{ABS} , on the basis of which the concentration Mg was founded, in leaves of *A. platanoides*, was less by 76.6% compared to the leaves of *A. tataricum* (at $p \leq 0,05$).

The results of the study showed that the concentration of MnO_2 and MgO_2 in the composition of aerosols on the sanitary protection zone of the plant of building structures in atmospheric air is higher, than in the control areas,

located on the territory of Navodnitsky Park remote from of the plant. These conditions cause a decrease in the effectiveness of the photosynthetic apparatus *A. platanoides*, as well as darkening, wrinkling's, early aging and to defoliations of leaves.

The most adapted to the effects of Mn, Mg and dust particles where are the leaves of *A. tataricum*, therefore, the spread of this species of Acers on the territories of the sanitary protection zones of construction plant will help to ensure the productivity of photosynthesis, increase in oxygen supply to the atmosphere, and reduce the impact of the activities of enterprises. We believe that the results of the study should be taken into account when developing environmental projects for greening the sanitary-protection zone of construction plants in industrial cities.

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